

The Florida Project

In the Shadow of Disney: Exploring Class Systems and Society in Florida

Figure 1. Moonee and Jancey look at a rainbow
Note. From *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017).

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May 2024

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The Florida Project (2017)

Introduction

This paper will critically analyze the film *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017) through a socio-economic lens.

To investigate how the notion of poverty influences the story, the following themes will be explored: the capitalist systems of America, social structures, wealth disparities and class hierarchies. By investigating these themes, this paper will examine the aim of this work: supporting the audience to empathize with the lower class within the holiday destination of Florida.

Synopsis of the film

The social realist drama film *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017), follows the playful, naïve and mischievous six-year-old Moonee (Brooklyn Prince) living with her young and irresponsible mother Halley (Bria Vinaite). They live in a motel run by grumpy but caring manager Bobby (Willem Dafoe) a couple of minutes away from Disney World. Set over the course of summer break, the film follows Moonee as she goes on adventures with her friends while the motel residents struggle to make ends meet.

Director background

American independent filmmaker Sean Baker is known for films such as *Anora* (Baker, 2024), which won the Academy Award for Best Picture, and *Tangerine* (Baker, 2015), which was shot entirely on an iPhone. His films tell stories of the underdogs of society and are created with small budgets within a social realism style (Baker, 2017).

Taking inspiration from 'The Little Rascals' (McGowan, 1922) Sean Baker juxtaposed his story about the life of a happy upbeat child against the impoverished residents of a motel in the shadow of Disney World.

In an interview with *The Upcoming* (2017) Baker states 'The Little Rascals focused on the mischievous adventures of little children but it was set against the Great Depression... a lot of the characters were living in poverty, but it never focused on that. It focused really on the joy of being a child.' (Baker, 2017)

Socio-economic Analysis of The Florida Project

The United States projects itself as being the home of the free, and the brave, where everyone has equal rights. These beliefs stem from the Declaration of Independence (National Archives, 2023), they are deeply rooted in American culture and one of the core values presented internally and externally towards the rest of the world.

'...We hold these truths to be self-evident, that all men are created equal, that they are endowed by their Creator with certain unalienable Rights, that among these are Life, Liberty and the pursuit of Happiness.--That to secure these rights, Governments are instituted among Men, deriving their just powers from the consent of the governed, --That whenever any Form of Government becomes destructive of these ends, it is the Right of the People to alter or to abolish it, and to institute new Government, laying its foundation on such principles and organizing its powers in such form, as to them shall seem most likely to effect their Safety and Happiness.' (National Archives, 2023)

American society holds the Declaration of Independence as a key value for their way of living. In 'So You're an American? A Guide to Answering Difficult Questions Abroad' written by the State Department, independence is described as 'Independence, also called freedom or liberty, also represents the limited intervention and control of the government on personal lives. This notion of independence comes directly from this Declaration of Independence.' (U.S. Department of State, 2020)

In 2012, former president of the United States, Barack Obama gave a speech in front of Cinderella's Castle at the leisure Park and holiday destination Disney World connecting Disney, tourism and the American spirit. This speech accurately captures the American ideology and spirit that the country is projecting towards the rest of the world.

'Every year, tens of millions of tourists all over the world come to visit America. Makes sense. You got the greatest country on Earth- people want to come... This is the land where we do big things, and so have incredible landmarks, like the Golden Gate Bridge and the Empire State Building; the Hoover Dam; the Gateway Arch. This is the land of iconic cities and all their sights-- from Independence Hall in Philadelphia to Faneuil Hall in Boston, from the Space Needle in Seattle to the skyline of my hometown in Chicago. But I'm here today because I want more tourists here tomorrow. I want America to be the top tourist destination in the world... Ultimately, that's how we're going to rebuild an economy where hard work pays off, where responsibility is rewarded, and where anybody can make it if they try. That's what America is all about. That's part of the reason why people want to come here because they know our history. They know what the American Dream has been all about. And a place like Disneyland represents that quintessentially American spirit.' (National Archives, 2012)

Figure 2. Declaration of Independence (1776)
Note. From National Archives (2023).

Figure 3. President Obama's speech at Disney World.
Note. Official White House photograph (Hebert, 2012), from National Archives (2012).

However, the American spirit doesn't work for everyone as it excludes the lower classes. Although the United States presents itself to the world as a well-off rich country, this is far from the truth. In 2021 37.9 million people were living in poverty in America, with 16.8% of them being children. (Deutchman et al., 2022)

Figure 4. *Distribution of child poverty in American counties*
 Note. Osceola County shown in dark blue (17–24.9%). From U.S. Census Bureau (Benson, 2022).

There is a lot of poverty across America with many people in need, they are not supported by their government. For example, in the United States, there is no law regarding the right to housing which leads to a lot of inequality. For the poorest people, the lack of housing leads to the inability to influence this right.

'the greatest, most unique challenge for voters experiencing homelessness is the inability to register without proof of address' (National Conference of State Legislatures, 2021)

This indicates that homeless people are unable to vote for change and thereby have no voice when it comes to the right to housing, they become powerless against the American system. This is contradicting the American Declaration of Independence whose main concern should be to give all American citizens equal rights.

Ironically, Obama gave his speech about the American spirit at Florida's Disney World. The country wants to show the majestic sites and their incredible accomplishments but is blind to the negative side, the poverty of many less than ten minutes away.

According to American cultural researcher Dr S. Mittermeier (2020),

"The theme park has become shorthand for excitement, fairy-tale endings, (American) dream(s) come true. However, it has also been used as a metaphor for the United States as a whole, often in a critical fashion – Disneyland as the epitome of the fake, the phony, the unreal." (Mittermeier, 2020)

It is this marginalized group of American citizens that *The Florida Project* chooses to focus on; the people who are often overlooked. Director Sean Baker stated in an interview with Medium that when *"making films about the USA, I feel the obligation to show the melting pot...So if I'm making a film that makes a statement about the United States and this era, it had better be all-inclusive."* (Baker, 2021)

Social Realism and Poverty in America

The film style Social Realism acts as a commentary on the social class system and critiques the political state. It focuses on the class systems and depicts the working class and their way of life. Social Realist films often hire unknown actors to create an authentic feeling and look for actors who have a close connection to the people they portray. Common themes depicted in Social Realism are

“rebellious protagonists, tough speech, stories of disenchanting youth and drinking and brawling” (Thoma, 2021)

“By juxtaposing the dominant culture so strongly, social realism films portray the notion of the growing gap between the different classes and the fight to have their voices heard. Socialist realism was created as a means to promote government propaganda and “propagate the Communist party’s policies and ideology” (Thompson & Bordwell, 2019, p. 235)

They utilise modernist techniques such as *“fast motion to suggest excitement during the hero’s crimes and handheld camerawork for his exhilarating open-air jogging”*. (Thompson & Bordwell, 2019, p. 407)

Another aspect is the location shooting for ‘authenticity’ and honest down-to-earth depiction of characters to make the audience sympathise with the characters. In America, filmmakers have taken inspiration from the British New Wave and evolved it into their own form of filmmaking which

“portrays both the realism of the working class and the inherent need for escapism that comes alongside it” (McCausland, 2021)

The Florida Project is a Social Realist Drama. Most actors had no prior acting experience and the extras, as well as Christopher Rivera portraying Scooty, are actual motel residents.

The film was shot on location in the Magic Castle Inn, Osceola County. Just outside of Disney World, there are multiple motels with impoverished residents, a clear indication of a class divide. Disney World markets itself to the middle class from all over the world encouraging them to visit the theme park, while people living nearby can’t afford to go there. Even though Disney is not the cause of their poverty, setting the story in this place creates a powerful contrast and forces the audience to look past the magical world of Disney.

The main aim of Social Realist movies is to draw attention to the socio-economic conditions of the working class and depict an accurate and respectful portrayal of those living in it. The audience observes their stories without exaggeration, it isn’t an exploitation of their trouble purely, so the audience can feel better about themselves and their own lives.

Based on the articles ‘5 Reasons poverty porn empowers the wrong person’ (Roeningk, 2014) and ‘Poverty, porn, and the picture : exploring representation of exploitative media through the case of Oxfam’ (Mascovich, 2017) the conclusion can be made that while trying to be realistic, movies about the impoverished can frequently come out as exploitative and patronizing. This so-called ‘poverty porn’ is in the film and television industry generally defined as media that fetishize poverty or exploits the poor’s condition for the entertainment of audiences.

Films like *City of God* (Meirelles & Lund, 2002), *Slumdog Millionaire* (Boyle, 2008), *Pixote: The Law of the Weakest* (Babenco, 1980), *Salaam Bombay!* (Nair, 1988), and *Cyclo* (Tran, 1995) have been criticized for portraying poverty porn. In an interview (RTE, 2009) with the radio RTE, writer Priya Rajsekar discusses the representation of the slums of Mumbai in the movie *Slumdog Millionaire*.

"...it's such a stereotypical image of what people would expect slums to be. But, you know, there is a lot of pride and dignity there in those slums, which are not represented in the movie, and that's the biggest, you know, disappointment that I had... He (director Danny Boyle) was there making a commercial movie and it was a very cleverly executed collaboration of commerce and art. I don't think there was any intention to educate the audience there." (Rajsekar, 2009)

The movie fits its main purpose: to entertain, but this doesn't mean that it's not insensitive towards its subject.

Baker's film depicts class disparities and poverty in a respectful way. The story doesn't get sidetracked by the hardships nor only blame the protagonist. There is no glorification of its characters who are presented without painting them as either heroes or villains. The film depicts the characters free from judgement, leaving that up to the audience. Instead, it merely shows who they are and their reality. The film tries to broaden the viewer's perspectives of what life is really like for those on the edge of society, emphasizing that a person's social status doesn't determine whether they are a good or bad person.

All the characters are struggling to make ends meet, and they support one another. The consequences of poverty vary from person to person, and whether there is a positive or negative outcome depends on the moral decisions made in the given circumstances.

'The Florida Project' highlights how the social systems perpetuate poverty and its vicious cycle. Instead of concentrating only on limitations, the movie reveals how and what motivates the characters to keep pushing forward. By presenting the story of class through a social realism style, *'The Florida Project'* offers an authentic portrayal of the motel residents in Osceola County. Despite the Declaration of Independence's promise of equal rights for all American citizens, this is not the case. The film encourages viewers to be more empathetic towards those outcasted and to help understand why people make certain choices in inequitable circumstances.

Story: plot, editing and cinematography

The Florida Project does not follow a classic story structure, but instead is told in a linear day-to-day structure edited in a style called 'Cinema Verité'. As Dancyger (Dancyger, 2019, p. 216) describes, 'Cinema Verité' is an approach that creates a general sense of authenticity and captures the true and raw personalities of the characters.

It is a natural and semi-observational style that focuses on characters and situations rather than a structured plot. Without clearly indicating time, the scenes seem to just breeze past, not trying to film a specific outcome or direct the audience's opinion using narration, music, etc.

In an interview with Film Comment (2017) director Sean Baker states,

'For this film I wanted the audience to feel like they've spent the summer with these characters. And when has your summer ever been plot-driven? No, you're just meandering through your summer. I felt it had to be just a series of events, not bound to a plot.' (Baker, 2017)

It feels like a kid playing outside until called in for dinner. There is no time until something important happens.

The Cinema Verité editing style goes hand in hand with a film technique called 'fly-on-the-wall'. In this style, the audience is observing the scene as if being 'a fly on the wall'. Based on an article by Studio Binder (Leonard, 2019) this film making style can be described as the following, It makes the story feel true to life and it's often easier to connect with the characters. There are no dramatic zoom-ins or harsh cuts. Instead, with the use of handheld shots and loud environmental sounds the camera drifts through the scene, objectively recording the events as they unfold. For example, when the helicopters fly in the background, parts of the dialogue can't be heard, just like people would have trouble understanding each other with a loud helicopter close by.

Figure 5. Helicopter scene at the Magic Castle motel Note. Still from *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017).

Enhanced by the cinematography and editing the plot of the movie could loosely be separated into two halves.

The first half of the movie is mostly focused on Moonee making and losing friends, creating mischief, and finding things to do. The film shows Moonee's view of all the beauty and happiness of her world but ignores the struggling adults around her as she is unaware of the situation. Most adults try to shield children from bad things and trouble, in *The Florida Project* manager Bobby does this multiple times. The audience is put into the position of a child so they get shielded and protected from seeing bad things. This results in Halley's story being told in the background. When an important moment for Halley happens, the camera is not placed with her, but instead with Moonee, who is just playing in the bathtub. In the first half, Halley has just gotten fired from her job, because she refused to do sex work, but is trying to find new ways of earning money and is having fun with her friend.

It is in the second half of the film, that bad situations start to appear which cannot be ignored. Instead of distracting the audience with Moonee's world, the film now shows Halley stealing and getting violent. On top of that it is revealed that each time Moonee is in the bathtub, Halley has been working as a prostitute in the other room.

It is in this half that the audience realizes this life is not sustainable. No matter how desperately Halley tries to give her child the best and happiest life, the plot builds towards the question, when Moonee will be taken away?

To outline the film's narrative and socio-economic lens, two scenes will be analysed that explore the illusion of escapism in America.

Scene 1 – Tourists and class difference

When two lost tourists end up at the Magic Kingdom Motel, they are heavily disappointed as it is not a hotel on the Disney premises as they wanted. Apart from having booked the wrong motel, it also shows them a low-class world. As shocking as it is for the tourist to see this other side of Florida, it also shows Moonee and Scooty another look of the world. They witness how higher-class people look down on them. The tourists describe their home, their world, with disdain as 'a welfare motel' and don't want to stay there under any circumstances. People like to turn a blind eye and live life ignoring those living in desperation. Tourists don't want to see slums and the reality of people actually living in Osceola County, they want to see the perfect world Disney promised them. In the scene, ending up at the motel results in a shattering of the tourist's reality which they were not ready for.

The lost tourist scene is visually different from the rest of the movie. *The Florida Project* shows a peek into Moonee's world. The colours are loud and vibrant like her, but also in pastel shades fitting the innocence of children. It makes life seem much better than it is. The world is magical, there is so much to explore and fun things to do, Moonee doesn't see the bad things.

Figure 6. Cinematography reflecting Moonee's perspective
Note. Still from *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017).

In this scene, however, the colours are dull, sombre, beige and greyish tones with harsh uninviting TL light. This is the reality for the adults. The tourists are upset because this is not the America they want to see. They are looking for a strong happy America, an escapist fantasy. But now, arriving in the Magic Kingdom motel they are confronted with reality, with this other side of America. It pops their bubble, the fake façade with Disney's happy colours are gone.

Figure 7. Cinematography reflecting the tourists' perspective
Note. Still from *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017).

The lost tourist scene shows how thin the line between the two worlds is, as both the adults and children come to understand. Once you cross it, the illusion will no longer be the same and trying to go back to this ignoring reality from before is incredibly difficult.

Scene 2 – The Ending and Escapism

In the last scene of *The Florida Project*, Child Protection Services comes to take Moonee away, but she escapes. It's at this point that the audience realises that Moonee understands more about the world than she lets on. This is difficult for the adults to admit, as they realise, she hasn't been protected from the bad things of this world and understands that her real, happy, life with her mother is ending. So, Moonee flees (temporarily) to a world where she is in control, starting a dream sequence where she runs off with her friend Jancee to the commercialized happiness: Disney World.

According to American cultural researcher Dr S. Mittermeier (2020), In 1955, when Disneyland opened,

'It provided reassurance during the confusing times of the early Cold War by reveling in civil religion and patriotic spirit, nurturing the conservative values lived by the families in the newly-built suburbs. But it also reflected the paradoxes of the years: nostalgia for the past and hope for the future, foreignness and familiarity, rugged individualism, and national community...Disneyland delivered all of this in a package deal; a clean, safe, privately owned environment, a true "happiest place on Earth" . (Dr S. Mittermeier, 2020 p.188-189)

Disney takes you on a journey to a different world, the attractions show different places, times and environments focusing on the senses and people's emotions. (Dr S. Mittermeier, 2020 p.5)

They create a place where fantasy feels real, capitalizing on people's longing for escapism, for entertainment, for leisure.

'For a place that reflects their culture, their values and the zeitgeist, as well as providing a much-needed break from it.' (Dr S. Mittermeier, 2020 p.194)

But this 'happiest place on earth' as Disney likes to claim provides only an escape for those who can afford their high price tag. The lower-class Florida residents, the ones in the most need of an escape, are not permitted one.

The ending scene is stylistically different from the rest of the movie, as it breaks away from the Cinema Verite style. Apart from the opening credits, it's the first time that the audience hears music that's not located within the scene. Until now the music came from phones and speakers that the characters and thereby the audience can hear. This keeps in with the realistic tone and lets audiences form their own opinions on what the emotions of the characters are, instead of forcing an emotion on them. In the dream sequence, however, there is suddenly artificially added music creating a stark contrast with the rest of the movie.

The camera also changes drastically in the dream sequence. *The Florida Project* is shot on 35mm film giving everything a hazy summer holiday feel. The dream sequence however is shot on iPhone. As director Sean Baker stated in an interview with The Hollywood Reporter (2017),

'I was using the iPhone 6s Plus for The Florida Project, and it has what's called a rolling shutter, and it gave it this hyperactivity and a very different, jarring feel, and we liked that.'
(Baker, 2017)

Figure 8. Moonee and Jancee entering Disney World
Note. Still from *The Florida Project* (Baker, 2017).

Enhanced by the cinematography changes, the switch from reality to fantasy is a stark contrast with the rest of the movie, making it feel out of place. *The Florida Project* has been as realistic as possible but now the audience is forced to watch a fantasy escape that they know is not real and that the characters will never be able to experience. It is unfair, like a betrayal. The audience has seen over a hundred minutes of the movie, so they are entitled to have their questions answered. Right?

They want to see a hero, a happy ending or at the very least, deserve a clear resolution. That's how (Hollywood) films work, that's the system they're used to. But isn't this the whole point of the movie? This is a story where the audience gets a look into the lives of the forgotten people of society, those struggling in the system. They are surviving, pushing forward even though there might not be hope for a happy ending. So why should the audience deserve one?

Conclusion

The Florida Project is a thought-provoking Social Realist film that delves into the complex world of poverty and class disparity in America. Set near Disney World, the film shows the daily struggles of the impoverished residents of the Magic Kingdom motel using a Cinema Verité style to capture the raw emotions and experiences of the characters. *The Florida Project* sheds light on the harsh reality that core American values are not easily achievable for everyone with a system that preserves poverty. Those marginalized are not permitted escapism, it stays out of reach for those belonging to the lower class. However, the ending scene shows a dream sequence where the main character flees to fantasy. The film offers a glimpse into the lives of those living on the edge of society and tries to show why people make certain decisions in their circumstances. On paper, some decisions might look entirely good or bad. However, the film demonstrates the characters' situations and encourages viewers to not rush to judge people, but instead approach those outcasted and marginalized with an open mind and empathy. *The Florida Project* challenges the viewers' perceptions to make a more thoughtful approach to issues of poverty and inequality.

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